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BEYOND RISK PREDICTION: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ADAPTIVE RESILIENCE

Traditional approaches to ensuring the security of socio-technical systems, based on risk prediction and threat prevention, demonstrate critical limitations in the context of unprecedented growth in system complexity, emergence of fundamentally new types of threats, increasing rate of environmental changes, and global interconnectedness of information and socio-technical systems, where local incidents can trigger cascade effects with catastrophic consequences.

The purpose of this paper is to provide a concise conceptual and terminological description of a new security paradigm based on the principles of adaptive resilience.

In this context, **resilience** is defined as the ability of a complex open, nonlinear, dissipative system to maintain fundamental invariants and perform critical functions under conditions of deterministic chaos and bifurcation phenomena (caused by environmental changes and destructive factors), ensuring directed self-organization, evolution, and selection of optimal development trajectories within the space of permissible states through the enhancement of adaptive potential and entropy dissipation mechanisms.

The invariants of a socio-technical system comprise a set of fundamental structural-functional characteristics and attributive properties that determine the ontological essence of the system and define the boundaries of permissible morphogenesis during adaptation. Changes in these invariants result in either loss of system identity or degradation of the system's target function.

Based on interdisciplinary analysis integrating complex systems theory, the concept of adaptation energy, and the method of correlation adaptometry, we have formulated definitions for the key concepts of the paradigm. The mechanisms for ensuring resilience through adaptive potential management are proposed, encompassing structural plasticity, resource flexibility, and fractal diversity in the implementation of critical functions. This developed approach establishes a theoretical foundation for designing next-generation security systems capable of utilizing uncertainty as a developmental factor.

A key element of the proposed approach to ensuring resilience is the iterative enhancement of adaptive potential, which includes determining critical stability thresholds, assessing the current level of adaptive resources, and forecasting their depletion. Here, **adaptive potential** is defined as an emergent characteristic of a complex system that determines its capacity for structural-functional reconfiguration and modification of connection topology in response to exogenous and endogenous stressors. The concept of adaptive potential is grounded in H.Selye's adaptation energy theory, first proposed in 1938 [1].

For quantitative assessment of the adaptive potential level, the correlation adaptometry method [2] is proposed, which is based on analyzing correlations between system parameters during adaptation and their variances, enabling evaluation of the system's state under external factors. The method builds upon the observation that the degree of complex systems' adaptation is reflected in changes of correlations between their key parameters. Studies of correlation and variance dynamics in systems adapting to environmental factor loads revealed a universal effect in ensembles of systems under similar factor loads: during crisis, typically before the appearance of obvious system destruction symptoms, both correlation and variance (and volatility) increase. However, successful adaptation leads to their reduction.

In light of the aforementioned evidence, it can be posited that the management of correlations and variances in key system parameters facilitates the intentional enhancement of its adaptive capacity, which is a pivotal factor in ensuring the resilience of socio-technical systems in the face of high uncertainty. Rather than allocating resources towards predicting the probability and consequences of risk realisation in conditions of fundamental unpredictability [3], it would be more prudent to direct efforts towards the development of the adaptive potential of socio-technical systems. This entails:

- Development of structural plasticity, defined as the system's ability for rapid dynamic reconfiguration of internal connections and processes. Structural plasticity is characterized by three primary parameters: reconfiguration speed, depth of possible changes, and transformation reversibility. Reconfiguration speed determines the system's ability to respond promptly to environmental changes through restructuring of internal interconnections. The depth of changes characterizes the scope of possible structural transformations without loss of system functionality. Reversibility defines the system's ability to return to its initial configuration after the cessation of stress factors. High levels of structural plasticity ensure system adaptation to a broad spectrum of impacts through optimization of internal organization. A key factor here is maintaining functional integrity during structural transformations, achieved through preservation of critical interconnections while simultaneously modifying auxiliary structures.

- Development of system resource flexibility. This mechanism encompasses two primary components: optimization of existing entropy dissipation resources and development of capability to detect and utilize new resource sources. Resource flexibility involves not only effective management of available resources but also the system's ability to redistribute resource flows in response to changes in external environment and internal system state. Of particular importance is the optimization of entropy dissipation processes, enabling the system to maintain a stable non-equilibrium state with minimal resource expenditure. A critical factor here is the system's ability to identify and engage alternative resource sources before existing ones are depleted, ensuring operational continuity under resource constraints.

▪ Iterative testing with sub-threshold stressors. This method is based on modeling critical scenarios that could potentially lead to irreversible loss of system functionality. A fundamental feature of the method is not only the assessment of current resilience levels but also the purposeful stimulation of the system's adaptive mechanisms development. During operation at the boundary of maximum capabilities, activation of latent system resources occurs, along with the formation of alternative pathways for critical functions implementation and enhancement of recovery mechanisms. Each iterative test acts as a catalyst for evolutionary changes in the system, stimulating qualitative development of its adaptive capabilities. A crucial factor in this mechanism's effectiveness is precise calibration of stressor intensity: they must be sufficiently strong to stimulate adaptive processes while not exceeding critical thresholds beyond which irreversible system degradation begins.

A significant aspect is the existence of critical thresholds beyond which the system loses its capacity for recovery and adaptation. This necessitates proper management of adaptation energy expenditure to prevent its depletion. Statistical evidence indicates that system destruction is frequently caused not by a single powerful impact, but by the cumulative effect of a series of less significant stresses that exhaust the adaptive potential.

To overcome critical thresholds, the concept of diversity in critical function implementation is proposed. Diversity represents a system organization principle wherein each critical function is supported by multiple independent implementation pathways. In essence, this represents a fractalization of critical function implementation paths, where each path maintains its own redundancy system. Such organization ensures system resilience to local failures and continuity of critical functions during disruptions in individual components.

The integration of the described mechanisms: structural plasticity, resource flexibility, and diversity - forms a new type of system architecture, capable not only of maintaining stability under uncertainty but also of utilizing stress impacts as a stimulus for development.

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